

DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATION OF DIPLOMATIC TEXTS

Mustafayeva Mokhiniso Oybekovna

Third-year student of Bukhara State University

Xaydarova Laylo Khamroyevna

Teacher at the Department of English Literature and Translation Studies of Bukhara State University

Abstract: *This article will describe diplomatic discourse in general and reveal its common problems in the translation field. As government policies all over the world negotiate with each other about this and that utilizing official business style, it becomes difficult for translators to interpret and translate their speech due to several issues arising in the speech, which will be discussed hereby and will be given several solutions to deal with them.*

Keywords: *diplomatic discourse, abbreviations, speech clichés.*

The topics of diplomatic discourse cover a wide range of problems affecting bilateral and multilateral relations states, cooperation between states in various fields, issues activities of international organizations, state missions for abroad, etc. For each state it seems possible identifying the range of issues that constitute priority areas of diplomatic activities of the state in the general structure of international relations.

Issues of relationships between states, concern for internal and external security, acts regulating their joint activities are fundamental to the diplomatic activities of any states and governments. One of the most important requirements that professional translator also must be competent in the field of politicians. The translator must understand the essence of political speech figures. The translator also needs to pay attention to established norms of language, norms and customs and cultural traditions [Minyar-Beloruhev, 1999: 17].

We view diplomatic communication in a broad sense, therefore we will operate with the concept of “diplomatic discourse”. Diplomatic discourse refers to the official business style of speech, represented by various forms of oral and written communication, such as: negotiations, notes, memos, memoranda, declarations, resolutions, statements, communiqués, etc. At the linguistic level it distinguished by the presence of its own terminology, a set of standard etiquette phrases, cliches and

lexical and grammatical units used as a means of influencing the recipient of information.

A feature of the translation of diplomatic texts is compliance with strict rules for using standard language templates. The translator must have business etiquette skills. [Ismagilova, 2012: 58] One of the features of translating diplomatic texts is that abbreviations of the source text should be decrypted and transmitted according to generally accepted rules, but if in the original language there are abbreviations that cannot be deciphered, then such abbreviations are usually transcribed. One of the main distinguishing features of business style is using words in their direct dictionary meaning. It should be noted, that when translating such texts one can not use one word in different meanings, just as you can not use either contextual meanings or emotionally charged meanings of words.

Translations of diplomatic texts must be absent syntactic structures of the source language, and it must satisfy generally accepted norms of the target language. [Ismagilova, 2012; 59]

The translator must take into account all language features diplomatic discourse, which include, according to T.A. Volkova, the presence of speech cliches, phraseological units, borrowed vocabulary, neologisms, and so on. Diplomatic speech is also often abound of quotes, expressions of famous people, which means that the translator must have basic knowledge of history, cultural studies, etc. [Volkova, 2007].

Let us note the main stylistic characteristics of diplomatic text that determine the translation strategy: objectivity; generality; information content; logical organization of presentation; semantic clarity, certainty; strict adherence to diplomatic ethics. Word usage in diplomatic text is characterized by the following features: the use of speech cliches ; specific semantic fields of significant parts of speech (defined, along with key points and values of diplomatic discourse, character and subject of the document); terminological (diplomatic) vocabulary; borrowing; euphemisms; abbreviations, special symbols and designations. The structural identification of translation and original is that the translation receptors believe that the translation does not reproduce the original only in general, but also in particulars, the exact order of presentation is assumed translator of the original content: number and content of sections, parts, chapters must match.

Conclusion. To summarise, it should be noted that, the translator in order to translate a diplomatic discourse properly according to rules of official business style should be acquainted with the language norms, understand an essence of speech figures and have knowledge other fields, such as history and culture.

REFERENCES:

1. Аникина Ю.В., Владимирова С.В. Сущность политических переговоров // Взаимодействие науки и общества: сб. статей Междунар. научно-практич. конф.: в 4 ч. Ч. 4. Уфа: АЭТЕРНА, 2016. С. 164–166.
2. Арутюнова Н.Д. Дискурс // Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь. М.: Сов. Энциклопедия. 1990. С. 136–137.
3. Бархударов Л.С. Язык и перевод. М.: Международные отношения, 1975. 201с.
4. Бахтин М.М. Проблема речевых жанров // Бахтин М.М. Литературно-критические статьи. М.: Художественная литература, 1986. С. 428–472.
5. Бенвенист Э. Общая лингвистика – 3-е изд. М.: Эдиториал УРСС. 2009. 448 с.
6. Борисова Л.И. Лексико-стилистические трансформации. М., 2002. 189 с.
7. Борисова Л.И. Ложные друзья переводчика. М., 2002. 166 с.
8. Бреус Е.В. Основы теории и практики перевода с русского языка на английский: Учебное пособие. 2-е изд., испр. и доп. М.:Изд-во УРАО,2000.188 с.
9. Войков П.Л. Дипломатический словарь. В 3-х т. Глав. Ред. А.А. Громыко (и др.). М., Политиздат, 1971. 479 с.
10. Волкова Т.А. Дипломатический дискурс: лексико-семантические особенности и стратегии перевода. Самара: Самар. гос. акад. культуры и искусств, 2007. 258–264 с.
11. Nida E.A., Taber C.R. The Theory and Practice of Translation. E. J. Brill Publishing, 1982. 218 p.
12. Pearsall J. Oxford Dictionary of English. Oxford University Press, 2001. 2112 p.
13. Saville-Troike M. The Ethnography of Communication / M. Saville-Troike // Introduction. Oxford: Blackwell, 1982. P.6–25
14. Schäffner C. Translation Research and Interpreting Research. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters LTD, 2004. 135 p.